

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15333589

Relationship Between Parenting Styles And Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) Among Primary School Pupils In Rivers State, Nigeria

Josephine Israel Jaja

**Department of Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
josephineisraeljaja@gmail.com, 09038764009**

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among primary school pupils in Rivers state, Nigeria. The study was guided by five research questions and their corresponding null hypotheses. The design for the study is correlational research design. The population for the study consisted of all the 32,624 primary school pupils in the 338 public primary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 423 pupils was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in drawing the sample. Two instruments were used for the study namely the Parenting Styles Scale (PSS) and Conners' Rating Scales—Revised (CRS-R) for ADHD. The Research instruments were validated by the two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha (α) technique was used for all the instruments. The alpha coefficients of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.87 for Parenting Styles Scale (PSS) and Conners' Rating Scales—Revised (CRS-R) for ADHD respectively. The data generated were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. Specifically, research question 1-4 were answered using simple linear regression while research question five was answered using multiple regression. Regarding the hypotheses, hypotheses 1-4 were tested using t-test associated with simple linear regression while hypotheses five was tested using ANOVA associated with multiple linear regression. Result revealed among others that parenting styles significantly independently and jointly relate with ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended amongst others that parents should try and use more of authoritative parenting as this will help to reduce the level of ADHD among children.

Keyword: Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive, Uninvolved parenting style, Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

INTRODUCTION

Every level of schooling build upon the foundation of primary education. And there lots of challenges that are associated with primary education. A person's ability to succeed academically in higher education is directly related to how well they manage this challenge. Pupils with learning challenges, behavioural issues, emotional difficulties, or any other kind of disability or difficulty do not get specialized treatment. As a consequence of the nation's faltering economy, more parents are enrolling their children in public primary schools, which has led to a surge in the school pupil body and disrupted classroom operations for certain school pupils. Problems like Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) are one example. A

mental or behavioural disease known as ADHD impacts a person's ability to focus on tasks and obligations.

At home and in the classroom, many children who suffer from ADHD have substantial and persistent academic, social-emotional, and behavioural symptoms (DuPaul & Stoner, 2023; Clark et al., 2022). Adults and children alike are not immune to the effects of ADHD. The CDC reports that about 11 percent of children diagnosed with ADHD are between the 4–17 age range (CDC, 2021). Two studies have revealed that adults may have a prevalence of 2 percent to 5 percent of ADHD (Faraone, et al., 2020; Kessler et al., 2020).

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent patterns of inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity that interfere with daily functioning. It is categorized into three subtypes: inattentive, hyperactive-impulsive, and combined presentations. The inattentive type involves difficulty focusing, organizing tasks, following through on instructions, and frequent forgetfulness, which can lead to academic and social challenges. The hyperactivity/impulsive type is marked by restlessness, excessive talking, difficulty sitting still, and impulsive behaviors like interrupting or acting without considering consequences. The combined type includes symptoms from both categories and is the most common subtype of ADHD. These symptoms can significantly disrupt a child's academic, social, and emotional development, often persisting into adulthood if left untreated.

Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a commonest neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by impulsivity and restlessness, affecting all age groups with variation in prevalence rate and symptom presentation in children, adolescents, and adults. According to DSM IV criteria, ADHD is defined as inattention, including increased distractibility and difficulty sustaining attention, poor impulse control and decreased self-inhibitory capacity, and motor overactivity and restlessness in a child than expected for someone of that age and developmental level. Global epidemiological prevalence of 5.3% is one of the most common mental illnesses in childhood and adolescence (Banaschewski, et al. 2017).

ADHD is one of the most common childhood brain disorder which can continue through childhood and adolescents. ADHD is a prevalent childhood mental health condition affecting 7.8% of the school-aged population. It is characterized by developmentally atypical levels of inattention, activity, and impulsivity. Banaschewski, et al. (2017) in their recent research indicated that the symptoms of ADHD persist past childhood and adolescence well into college age and beyond. This can cause a variety of problems in numerous domains, including academics, social adjustment, school adjustment, work and home. Children with ADHD who attend primary school may have a more difficult time dealing with academic work, social and career planning. Symptoms of ADHD include difficulty staying focused and paying attention, difficulty controlling behaviour, and hyperactivity (over-activity). These symptoms can make it difficult for a child to succeed in school, get along with other children or peers. Those with ADHD also tend to move constantly and are impulsive, not thinking before acting (Kim, et al, 2022).

However, it is not everyone who is overly hyperactive, inattentive, or impulsive that has ADHD. After all, most children sometimes blurt out things they do not mean to say, jump from one task to another, or become disorganized and forgetful. It therefore depends on the degree; the diagnosis requires that such behaviour be demonstrated to a degree that is inappropriate for the person's age. The behaviours must create a real handicap in at least two areas of one's life, like home and the classroom, or the classroom and on the playground. Thus, a child who exhibits some symptoms but whose academic performance or social life is not impaired would not be diagnosed with ADHD. The diagnostic guidelines contain specific requirements for determining when the symptoms indicate ADHD. This is used by parents, teacher's counsellors or anybody taking care of the child to identify those with the disorder (Kim, et al. 2020). Parents been the closest and the first socialization agent of a child are in a better position to monitor and diagnose such disorder. Parenting (or child rearing) is the process of promoting and supporting the physical, emotional, social, and intellectual development of a child from infancy to adulthood. Parenting refers to the aspects of raising a child aside from the biological relationship (Martin, 2020). A high-quality parent-child relationship is critical for healthy development (Rasool, et al. 2020). Suffice it to say that the parenting style adopted by parents tremendously influence growth, development and future life

opportunities of a child. Parenting style, therefore is a psychological construct representing standard strategies that parents use in their child rearing. Style of parenting could also influence children ADHD. According to Eriega (2010) parenting styles describe the constellation of strategies that parents adopt in rearing their children. Akhtar (2012) describe parenting styles as the broad patterns of childrearing practices, values and behaviour that determines the power, relationship and expectations between parents and their children. Parenting has been a salient topic for millennium, with some of the oldest religious and cultural texts establishing codes, standards, admonitions and counsel on the best ways on how to be a good parent and how to meet the responsibility of proper nurturing of children. In almost all cultures of human civilization, parenting is not just celebrated, but also cherished. Little wonder, it is considered a hallmark of maturity in most societies and a gateway to other responsibilities and privileges of adulthood. Like most subjects and issues that have generated sustained interest and popular concern, parenting has had both a long history and unfinished verdict. Various suggestions and guidelines abound on the best approach to being a parent. This is neither surprising nor novel, due to the significant role parenting has and can play in nurturing individuals and building societies. Civilizations have been established and nations formed on the alter and inspiration of parents. It is therefore on this basis that both public opinion and scholarly research have shown that parenting is a vital component of human development as it is often associated with positive outcome in children and adults such as cognitive and social competencies (Desjardin, et al. 2018).

As would be used in this study, parenting styles refers to the behaviour and strategies used by parents to control and socialize their children. The pattern of child rearing adopts by parents, influenced by cultural values and societal norms, and it may play a crucial role in shaping the development and management of ADHD symptoms (Loya, et al. 2020). Within Nigerian families, collectivist values, respect for authority, and an emphasis on academic excellence strongly influence parenting practices. There are four main parenting styles: authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, and uninvolved.

Authoritarian parents enforce strict rules without explanation, focusing on obedience and discipline, which can lead to well-behaved, often anxious or aggressive children who struggle with decision-making. Parents who adopts this parenting style have strict set of rules and regulations and required obedience. Whenever directives are flouted by the children, immediate and harsh punishment is given to enforce compliance. Children under this parenting are found to be unfriendly aggressive and lack of both initiatives and enthusiasm in carrying out activities.

Authoritative parents, in contrast, maintain a nurturing relationship while setting clear expectations, explaining the reasons behind their rules, and encouraging open communication. This is a flexible and democratic style of parenting in which parents provide warm guidance and reasonable control for their children while permitting them the opportunity to decide how to handle their responsibilities and challenges in life. Authoritative parents encourage discussions about family rules, as well as provide independence, autonomy and freedom, while encouraging children to think about their lives and the consequences of their behaviour. These enable children to have positive self-concept that leads to high performance and social competence. It could be observed that adolescents from authoritative parenting styles may be less involved in adolescent restiveness and defiant behaviour. This approach fosters confidence, responsibility, and emotional well-being in children.

Permissive parents are warm and indulgent, with few rules or expectations, leading to children who are often impulsive and struggle with permissive parenting style, although they typically have good social skills. Okebukola, et al. (2013) asserted that permissive parents permit their children to act as they please. According to Elias and Yee (2019) permissive parents believe that children have rights similar to adults. This style could be associated with accepting. Parents rarely exert control over the children's behaviour and not closely monitor their children's behaviour.

Uninvolved parents are emotionally detached and provide minimal guidance or support, which can result in children who are self-sufficient but may struggle with emotional and academic challenges (Yim, 2022). Uninvolved parents invoke such phrases as, "I don't care where you go," or "why should I care what you do?" Uninvolved parents rarely consider their children's input in decisions and they generally do not want to be bothered by their need (Kopko, 2012). Children from uninvolved parenting may want to be involved

in restive activities as a result of lack of control. Additionally, extended family members, like grandparents, often play a significant role in caregiving, contributing to a collective approach to parenting that blends traditional and modern influences (Kim, et al. 2021).

While the link between parenting styles and ADHD appears to be firmly established in the literature, they appear to be a dearth of literature regarding the parenting styles as predictors of ADHD. This has been exacerbated by the excessive emphasis on negative problems faced by children such as lack of social adjustment and school adjustment. This has not only influenced the way children are perceived, but have also shaped a large chunk of scholarly research in that direction.

Within Nigerian families, parenting practices are often influenced by a duality: balancing emotional support with high expectations for academic and personal success. This reflects cultural priorities emphasizing both collectivist values and family honor, which place significant pressure on parents to ensure their children excel academically (Rasool, et al. 2020). The patriarchal structures common in Nigeria communities further shape parenting dynamics, with gender disparities influencing expectations and treatment of children (Kim, et al. 2021). For instance, boys may face pressures to succeed academically and professionally, while girls may experience distinct expectations tied to traditional family roles (Kim, et al. 2021). Additionally, extended family members, like grandparents, often play a significant role in caregiving, contributing to a collective approach to parenting that blends traditional and modern influences (Kim, et al. 2021).

Despite the growing understanding of ADHD, research examining how Nigerian cultural, societal, and familial dynamics influence the diagnosis and management of ADHD remains scarce. Misinterpretation of ADHD symptoms within the context of cultural norms often delays diagnosis and leads to ineffective management strategies. Moreover, the limited representation of Nigerians in mental health research leaves critical gaps in developing culturally tailored interventions and support systems. This review seeks to address these gaps by exploring the relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state, Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. identify the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
2. determine the relationship between authoritative parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
3. examine the relationship between permissive parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
4. investigate the relationship between uninvolved parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
5. determine the joint role of parenting styles on the ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide this study

1. What is the extent of relationship between authoritarian parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?
2. To what extent is the relationship between authoritative parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?
3. What is the extent of relationship between permissive parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?
4. What is the extent of relationship between uninvolved parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?
5. What is the interactive joint relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed to guide this study

1. There is no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
2. There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
3. There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
4. There is no significant relationship between uninvolved (Laizer-faire) parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.
5. There is no significant joint relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was correlational research design. The population for the study consisted of all the 32,624 primary school pupils in the 338 public primary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 423 pupils was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in drawing the sample. Two instruments were used for the study namely the Parenting Styles Scale (PSS) and Conners' Rating Scales—Revised (CRS-R) for ADHD. The Research instruments were validated by the two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach alpha (α) technique was used for all the instruments. The alpha coefficients of 0.75, 0.82 and 0.87 for Parenting Styles Scale (PSS) and Conners' Rating Scales—Revised (CRS-R) for ADHD respectively. The data generated were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis. Specifically, research question 1-4 were answered using simple linear regression while research question five was answered using multiple regression. Regarding the hypotheses, hypotheses 1-4 were tested using t-test associated with simple linear regression while hypotheses five was tested using ANOVA associated with multiple linear regression.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of relationship between authoritarian parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?*

Table 1: Simple regression table showing the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.113a	.013	.010	5.88485

Data presentation on the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) showed that an R value of 0.113 was gotten with an R² value of 0.013 and an adjusted R² of 0.010. On the basis of the adjusted R² value obtained, it can be seen that authoritarian parenting style accounted for 1.0% variation in the attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Table 4:2: Summary of analysis, of simple regression associated with t-test on the extent to which authoritarian parenting style relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Beta			
1	(Constant)	17.227	1.191		1467	.000
	Authoritarian parenting style	.177	.075	.113	2.361	.019

The result in table 2 showed that the beta of .113 and a t-value of 2.361 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.019 which is less than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that authoritarian parenting style significantly relate to attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question: 2: *To what extent does authoritative parenting style relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?*

Table 3: Summary simple regression of the relationship between authoritative parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Adj Error of the estimate
.080a	.006	.004	5.90379

Table 3 Shows that the relationship between authoritative parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) yielded an R value of 0.080 this is, alongside a coefficient of determination R² of 0.006 and an adjusted coefficient of determination an (adj R²) of 0.004, it is deduced that 0.4% of the changes in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) are dependent on the changes of the effect of authoritative parenting style. On the other hand, the remaining, 99.6% of the changes in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among secondary school pupils are attributable to factors outside authoritative parenting style.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Table 4:4: Summary of analysis, of simple regression associated with t-test on the extent to which authoritative parenting style relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22.609	1.615		1001	.000
	Authoritative parenting style	-.145	.087	-.080	-1.667	.096

The result in table 4 showed that the beta of -.080 and a t-value of -1.667 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.096 which is higher than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that authoritative parenting style does not significantly relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The null hypothesis was therefore retained.

Research Question 3: *What is the extent of relationship between permissive parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?*

Table 5. Summary of simple regression of the relationship between permissive parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std error of the estimate
.169a	.028	.026	5.83803

In response to research question three, the result showed that a linear regression coefficient obtained for the relationship between permissive parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state, R value was 0.169, while the coefficient of determination, R² was 0.028, and the adjusted R² was 0.026. Based on R²value, it therefore indicates that 2.6% of the variations in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary

school pupils in Rivers state can be attributed and explained by their permissive parenting style while the remaining 97.4% can be attributed to other factors.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Table 4:6: Summary of analysis, of simple regression associated with t-test on the extent to which permissive parenting style relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.703	1.231		12.759	.000
	Permissive parenting style	.253	.071	.169	3.551	.000

The result in table 6 showed that the beta of .169 and a t-value of 3.551 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.000 which is less than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that permissive parenting style significantly relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Research Question Four: *What is the extent of relationship between uninvolved parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?*

Table 7: Regression coefficient of the relationship between uninvolved parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.138a	.019	.017	5.86647

From the result presented in Table 7 on the relationship between uninvolved parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state, an R-value of 0.138 was obtained with an R² value of 0.019 and an adjusted R² value of 0.017. From the R² it can be deduced that uninvolved parenting style accounted for about 1.7% of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?

Table 4:8: Summary of analysis, of simple regression associated with t-test on the extent to which uninvolved parenting style relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.719	1.085		20.009	.000
	Uninvolved parenting style	-.117	.069	-.081	-1.681	.094

The result in table 8 showed that the beta of .069 and a t-value of -1681 was obtained when the obtained regression coefficient was tested for significance, based on the sig-value of 0.094 which is higher than the alpha of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that uninvolved parenting style does not significantly relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The null hypothesis was therefore retained.

Research Question 5: *What is the interactive joint relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state?*

Table 9. Summary of multiple regression of the relationship between authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, permissive parenting style, uninvolved parenting style, social skills and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std error of the estimate
.252a	.064	.053	5.75821

The answer to research question six as shown in Table 9 indicated that a linear regression coefficient of 0.081 was obtained on the joint relationship between authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, permissive parenting style, uninvolved parenting style, social skills and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), with the coefficient of determination, R², of 0.252, and an adjusted R² of 0.06. From the adjusted R² value of 0.053, it therefore suggests that 5.3% of the variations in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among the ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state can be attributed and explained by authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, permissive parenting style, uninvolved parenting style, social skills.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant joint relationship between parenting styles and ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

Table 10: Multiple Linear Regression coefficient of the relationship between authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, permissive parenting style, uninvolved parenting style, social skills and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	961.228	4	192.246	5.798	.000 ^b
	Residual	14158.024	333	33.157		
	Total	15119.252	337			

Furthermore, in testing the corresponding null hypotheses, the result indicated that an F-value of 5.798 was obtained at 4 and 333 degrees of freedom with an associated p-value of 0.000. Since the obtained p-value was less than 0.05, it therefore indicates that authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, permissive parenting style and uninvolved parenting style do significantly jointly relate with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among the ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Authoritarian parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

The result of the research question one and its corresponding hypothesis one in table 1 revealed that there was a significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The relationship was statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance. This relationship between authoritarian parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state means that as the score on authoritarian parenting style increases, there was corresponding increase in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state and vice versa. This finding is not surprising to the researcher because authoritarian parents value obedience and use strict rules. They usually use punitive discipline tactics, have an absolute standard, restrict the autonomy of the child, are low in warmth, and do not use induction as a means of explaining their demands. It restricts freedom from the child thereby increasing the tendency of ADHD. This result is similar to that obtained by Alma (2022) who found out that majority of the parents used the authoritative style (94.5%). There was a significant relationship between parenting style and the risk of

ADHD in children with $P < 0.001$ for authoritarian and permissive styles and $P = 0.005$ for an authoritative style.

Authoritative parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

The result of research question two and the corresponding null hypothesis in table 4, revealed that there was no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The relationship was not statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance. This result implied that pupils who scored highly on the section of authoritative parenting style are prone to score high in their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). However, the reported positive relationship indicates that all those who are high in authoritative parenting style also scored high in their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). This result is not surprising to the researcher because in authoritative parenting style, the parents are nurturing, responsive, and supportive, yet set firm limits for their children. They attempt to control children's behavior by explaining rules, discussing, and reasoning. This result is similar to that obtained by Alma (2022) who found out that majority of the parents used the authoritative style (94.5%). There was a significant relationship between parenting style and the risk of ADHD in children with $P < 0.001$ for authoritarian and permissive styles and $P = 0.005$ for an authoritative style.

Permissive parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

The result of research question three and the corresponding null hypothesis in table 6, revealed that there was a significant relationship between permissive parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The relationship was statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance. The meaning of this result is that individual or pupils who are high in permissive parenting style will find it difficult in engaging to social activities. On the basis of the instrument administered, pupils who reported high values on the section permissive parenting style are most likely to score high on their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) as tested using the instrument for the study. Conversely those who score low on the section of permissive parenting style are most likely to score low in their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). In the study conducted by Alma (2022) who found out that majority of the parents used the authoritative style (94.5%). There was a significant relationship between parenting style and the risk of ADHD in children with $P < 0.001$ for authoritarian and permissive styles and $P = 0.005$ for an authoritative style.

Uninvolved parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)

The result of research question four and the corresponding null hypothesis in table 8, it was revealed that there was a significant relationship between uninvolved parenting style and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) among ADHD among primary school pupils in Rivers state. The relationship was statistically significant at 0.5 level of significance. This result implied that pupils who scored highly on the section of uninvolved parenting style are prone to score moderately in their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). However, the reported positive high relationship indicates that all those who score high in uninvolved also scored high in their attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). This result is also similar to the findings of Alma (2022) who found out that majority of the parents used the authoritative style (94.5%). There was a significant relationship between parenting style and the risk of ADHD in children with $P < 0.001$ for authoritarian and permissive styles and $P = 0.005$ for an authoritative style.

CONCLUSION

There is a significant relationship between parenting styles and ADHD in children. The dominant parenting style in this study is authoritative parenting. Parents who have children at high risk of ADHD mostly applied authoritarian parenting. Lack of parental attention through parenting can increase dopamine and norepinephrine levels in children, which is one of the causes of hyperactivity and will increase the risk of ADHD in children. More information about the condition of ADHD in children, the types of parenting as well as the advantages and disadvantages of each type of parenting is needed, so that parents can apply parenting styles appropriate to the child's condition.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Future research should focus on risk factors other than parenting that are thought to affect the risk of ADHD in children so that this condition can be minimised by early management.
2. All individuals entering different levels of education should have an ADHD assessment completed. This will allow those who have the condition to be identified and potentially treated, allowing them to reach their full potential and lead happy lives.
3. At all educational levels in Rivers State, and across Nigeria, counselling and psychotherapy have to be treated seriously as a means of assisting school pupils with behavioural problems and learning impairments in order to improve their social and cognitive capacities.
4. Parents should try and use more of authoritative parenting as this will help to reduce the level of ADHD among children.

References

- Akhtar, Z. (2012). *The effect of parenting style of parents on the attachment styles of undergraduate students*. www.languageinindia.com. Retrieved on 15th October, 2012.
- Alma, M. (2022). Relationship between Parenting Style and Risk of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder in Elementary School Children. *Malays J Med Sci*. 29(4):152–159.
- Banaschewski, T, Becker, K, Döpfner, M, Holtmann, M, Rösler, M, & Romanos M. (2017). Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*. 114(9):149–159
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2020). Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/adhd/data.html>
- Clark, C., Prior, M., & Kinsella, G. (2022). The relationship between executive function abilities, adaptive behaviour, and academic achievement in children with externalizing behaviour problems. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 43, 785–796.
- Desjardin, N, Dellavalle, R. P, & Morelli, J. G. (2018). Mailed intervention to promote sun protection of children: A randomized controlled trial. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*. 43(4):399–410.
- DuPaul, G. J., & Stoner, G. (2023). *ADHD in the schools: Assessment and intervention strategies*. Guilford Press.
- Eriega, E. G. (2010). Psychosocial determinants of school adjustment among secondary school students. *Ibadan Journal of Counselling*, 23 (2), 143-158.
- Faraone, S. V., Sergeant, J., Gillberg, C., & Biederman, J. (2020). The worldwide prevalence of ADHD: Is it an American condition? *World Psychiatry*, 2(2), 104-113.
- Kessler, R. C., Adler, L., Barkley, R., Biederman, J., Conners, C. K., Demler, O., Zaslavsky, A. M. (2020). The prevalence and correlates of adult ADHD in the United States: Results from the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 163(4), 716-723.
- Kim, K, Atkinson A, & Umemoto U. (2021). Asian cultural values and the counseling process: current knowledge and directions for future research. *Counselling Psychology*. 29:570–603.
- Loya, F, Reddy, R, & Hinshaw, S. P. (2020). Mental illness stigma as a mediator of differences in Caucasian and South Asian college students' attitudes toward psychological counselling. *Journal of Counselling Psychology*. 57:484–490.
- Okebukola, F., Owolabi, T., & Onafowokan, B.O. (2013). An assessment of the reading motivation skills of Nigerian primary school teachers: Implications for language and science education. *Reading & Writing* 4(1), Art. 33, 12
- Rasool, S, Zhang, J, & Aydin, H, (2020). The impact of South Asian parental involvement behaviors on children's academic achievement: instrument development and exploratory factor analysis. *New Waves Educ Res Dev J*. 24:21–52.
- Sanvictores, T, Mendez, M. D. (2024). *Types of parenting styles and effects on children*. StatPearls [Internet] Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing.
- Yim, E. P. (2022). Effects of Asian cultural values on parenting style and young children's perceived competence: a cross-sectional study. *Front Psychol*. 13:905093.